

The critical fibre break cluster for longitudinal tensile failure of unidirectional composites: misconceptions and new insights

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What is required for final failure of a fibre-reinforced polymer composite?

Damage mechanisms

- Fibre-matrix debonding
- Matrix cracking
- Fibre breaks
- Off-axis ply failure
- Delamination
- 0° ply failure

Longitudinal tensile failure of a UD ply

Stress redistribution around fibre break(s)

The critical cluster

14-plet in Scott et al. (2012)

94% of failure load

16-plet often assumed
as critical cluster size

Are observations even
possible?

Did it grow further
before final failure?

Did it trigger
final failure?

Modelling flow chart

Largest versus critical cluster

Largest cluster before final failure

Measures how stable clusters are

Can be easily tracked

Origin of critical cluster

All-carbon fibre composites

% of simulations where
largest = critical cluster?

Original size of critical
cluster?

Fibre-hybridisation

Randomly dispersed carbon/glass hybrid
5 hybrid volume fractions

largest cluster
= $f(\text{hybrid volume fraction})$?

Hybridisation stabilises
cluster development?

Modelling parameters

2000 fibres, $V_f = 50\%$
5 mm length
Elastoplastic matrix

Origin of critical cluster
1000 simulations

Fibre-hybridisation
200 simulations
HVF = 0,25,50,75,100%

Largest cluster size varies from simulation to simulation

Tracking clusters

3-plet

4-plet

5-plet

Origin of the critical cluster

21% of cases: largest cluster became critical cluster

Some from 0-plets

Effect of fibre-hybridisation

Hybridisation with glass fibres stabilises clusters

Very large hybrid effects

Conclusions

Origin of critical cluster

No direct link with largest cluster
Can develop from a 0-plet

Fibre-hybridisation

Stabilises clusters
→ Increases failure strain

Critical cluster

Concept = useful

Size = useless

→ Use largest cluster size instead

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Modelling parameters

2000 fibres, $V_f = 50\%$

5 mm length

Elastoplastic matrix

$r_{CF} = 3.5\mu\text{m}$

$\sigma_{0,CF} = 3500\text{MPa}$

$m_{CF} = 5$

$L_{0,CF} = 10\text{mm}$

Origin of critical cluster

1000 simulations

Fibre-hybridisation

200 simulations

HVF = 0,25,50,75,100%

$r_{GF} = 6\mu\text{m}$

$\sigma_{0,GF} = 2645\text{MPa}$

$m_{GF} = 4.52$

$L_{0,GF} = 25.4\text{mm}$